

ISic002991

I.Sicily inscription 002991

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2021-07-14 - Francesca Prado edited the text, tagged named entities and added English and Italian translation

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Original discovery not recorded.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 24.5 cm

Width 26.5 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [I(ησοῦς)] Χ(ριστός)
2. [---χ]ρησ τά χαῖρε
4. ἔζησες
5. ἔτη · κ ·

Apparatus

Text after Libertini 1949

Translation (en)

...farewell worthy...! You lived for 20 years.

Translation (it)

...addio, degna...! Vivesti 20 anni.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645341

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic002991>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4387879

Bibliography

Libertini, G 1949. Iscrizioni Centuripine. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 2: 91-97. At 96 no.2

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2021-07-14): ISic002991. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5104395>